

Hydrogen 1S-3S Data Format

Document Version 0.0

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File name and directory structure

The measurement program automatically create the folder with a name *yyyy.mm.dd* (*yyyy* is a year, *mm* month *dd* is a day). During the Hydrogen measurement the program place the file in the directory, which measurement starting time is correspondent the date. During Deuterium measurement the algorithm was changed: the files which was started before 9:00, is placed in the yesterday's folder (the measurements of Deuterium was quite usually done overnight).

In the moment of the data measurement start (pressing button "Start Measurement") the program creates file with name **H1s3s_***yyyy_mm_dd_hh_nn_ss.dat*, where the *_yyyy_mm_dd_hh_nn_ss* represents a date (I hope it is obvious).

File format

The measurement program writes the data into the ASCII files. The file consist of header and the table with data (TAB-separated values, separation character is ASCII tab #9).

Header

Description of Header

Line 1: *1s3s Measurement File. Program version 2.40*. The newer version of the program had similar file structure.

Line 2: *File header length : n_{head}* . By default there could be not less than $n_{head} = 20$ lines of text in header. Technically, everything which is written in the next lines is a text which was entered from free-text input window in measurement program. If user entered 18 or less lines, the header length is set to be 20 lines, the unused lines are just empty. If user entered more than $n_{user} > 18$ lines, the header length is set to $n_{head} = n_{user} + 2$, because 2 lines

describe program version and header length. In Deuterium measurement was many files with file header length more than 20.

Lines 3– n_{head} : Free text input, entered by user into the window in measurement program. This text should be parsed since it may contain File Header Parameters (FHP).

Line $n_{head} + 1$: Tab-separated headers of the column. This line is standard : *Frequency Signal1 Signal2 Signal3 Background Freq Foffset CavityPower1 Iteration Time TcryoA TcryoB VpPrepump PPrepumpN2 VpmainChamber PMainChamberN2 VpCryostat PCryostatN2 VpDischarge PDischargeN2 VpCombivac1 PCombivac1N2 VpCombivac2 PCombivac2N2 HFlow LsaFile LsaIntensityRatio LsaPeak LsaFwhm CavityPower2*

File Header Parameters

The FHPs are just an agreement to make the data processing more easy. The idea is that the processing program can interpret each line which has the form “*SomeString=SomeNumber*” as that the measurement file has the parameter called *SomeString* and its value is *SomeNumber*. The required is that the symbol = is fixed, *SomeString* is non-empty string, *SomeString* is a number (conversion of the string to numeric format doesn’t make cause an exception). Practically, it means that fitting program, when it forms a table with results, should create the additional columns into the this table, writing *SomeString* into the column header and *SomeNumber* in the column data field.

Data columns

0.1 Frequency

Frequency

Real value [Hz]. Column contain frequency set on synthesizer, which provide a signal on phase lock loop of Tsunami - Diode laser lock. In fact it is Tsunami offset frequency (offset from the Diode laser). In this document I designate it as *f*.

0.2 Signal1

Signal1

Integer value. Column number of counts on the detector 1 (big field of view, standing in the center).

0.3 Signal2

Signal2

Integer value. Column number of counts on the detector 2 (small field of view, standing downstream of the detector 1).

0.4 Signal3

Signal2

Integer value. Column number of counts on the detector 3 (small field of view, standing upstream of the detector 1).

0.5 Background

Background

Integer value. Column number of counts on the Doppler-broadened detector (stands on the other side of the lenses).

0.6 Frep

Frep

Real value [Hz]. Tsunami repetition rate. Will be designated as $f_{rep}^{Tsunami}$.

0.7 Foffset

Foffset

Real Value [Hz]. Difference between measured Tsunami offset frequency and set one. If more than 1 Hz - the PLL didn't work well, the point is bad.

0.8 CavityPower1

CavityPower1

Real value [V]. Voltage from the power measurement/cavity locking PMT.

0.9 Iteration

Iteration

Integer value. Number of scan in the current file.

0.10 Time

Time

Real value [days]. Delphi time of measurement of current point. Can be calculated from MJD using the formula $DelphiTime = MJD - 15018$. During the measurement the computer clock was set to local time, as the frequency measurement computer.

0.11 TcryoA

TcryoA

Real value [K]. Temperature of inner cryostat sensor (not the nozzle).

0.12 TcryoB

TcryoB

Real value [K]. Temperature of outer cryostat sensor (on the nozzle).

0.13 VpPrepump

VpPrepump

Real value [V]. Voltage from the vacuum gauge on the prepump.

0.14 PPrepumpN2

PPrepumpN2

Real value [mBar]. Voltage from the vacuum gauge on the prepump, recalculated to pressure of nitrogen according to formula in vacuum gauge specification.

0.15 VpmainChamber

VpmainChamber

Real value [V]. Voltage from the vacuum gauge in main volume of the vacuum chamber (long pipe far away from the detectors).

0.16 PMainChamberN2

PMainChamberN2

Real value [mBar]. Voltage from the vacuum gauge in main volume of the vacuum chamber, recalculated to pressure of nitrogen according to formula in vacuum gauge specification.

0.17 VpCryostat

VpCryostat

Real value [V]. Voltage from the vacuum gauge in cryostat.

0.18 PCryostatN2

PCryostatN2

Real value [mBar]. Voltage from the vacuum gauge in cryostat, recalculated to pressure of nitrogen according to formula in vacuum gauge specification.

0.19 VpDischarge

VpDischarge

Real value [V]. Voltage from the vacuum gauge in discharge.

0.20 PDischargeN2

PDischargeN2

Real value [mBar]. Voltage from the vacuum gauge in discharge, recalculated to pressure of nitrogen according to formula in vacuum gauge specification.

0.21 VpCombivac1

VpCombivac1

Reserved channel - was not used in the beginning. Later was used to measure the voltage from Thorlabs detector.

0.22 PCombivac1N2

PCombivac1N2

Not used, please ignore.

0.23 VpCombivac2

VpCombivac2

Reserved channel - was not used in the beginning. Later was used to measure the voltage from Thorlabs detector.

0.24 PCombivac2N2

PCombivac2N2

Not used, please ignore.

0.25 HFlow

HFlow

Real value[mln/min]. Flow of Hydrogen in millilitres in normal conditions per minute.

0.26 LsaFile

LsaFile

String. Recorded only if the LSA data receiving from network is switched ON. Name of the file where the data from LSA was recorded. If the data was not recorded, written the string "None".

0.27 LsaIntensityRatio

LsaIntensityRatio

Real value [dimensionless]. Recorded only if the LSA data receiving from network is switched ON. Column contains ratio of laser intensity on target wavelength to the peak of the laser intensity .

0.28 LsaPeak

LsaPeak

Real value [nm]. Recorded only if the LSA data receiving from network is switched ON. Column contains wavelength of the light where the peak of the spectrum (maximum spectral power) sits.

0.29 LsaFwhm

LsaFwhm

Real value [nm]. Recorded only if the LSA data receiving from network is switched ON. Column contains FWHM of the laser spectrum computed from received spectrum.

0.30 CavityPower2

CavityPower2

Real value [V]. Voltage from Thorlabs power meter.

Some important formulas for Hydrogen measurement

We are looking for the line near the expected frequency of 1S-3S(F=1) (CODATA 2014):

$$f_{base} = 2\,922\,742\,936\,722\,530 \text{ Hz}$$

The absolute frequency of the diode laser (AOM frequency around 410 MHz):

$$f_{ref}(820nm) = 1\,461\,379 \times 250 \text{ MHz} + 2 \times 60 \text{ MHz} - 150 \text{ MHz} - f_b,$$

where f_b is a beatnote frequency, recorded by the frequency comb computer (channels 3 and 4 redundant).

The data processing code can fit the data, using as a frequency axis the number f from the first column in the file. The fit center f_0 can be recalculated to the absolute frequency of the line transition (Tsunami lockbox invert OFF regime):

$$f_{abs}(102nm) = 8 \times (f_{ref}(820nm) - f_0) + 4 \times N_{Tsunami} \times f_{rep}^{Tsunami},$$

where $f_{rep}^{Tsunami}$ is Tsunami repetition rate (written in correspondent column of the data file). The integer number of Tsunami modes between transition frequency and reference laser $N_{Tsunami}$ can be calculated as:

$$N_{Tsunami} = \text{Floor} \left(\left(\frac{f_{base}/8 - f_{ref}(820nm)}{f_{rep}^{Tsunami}/2} \right) \right).$$

Here *Floor* is a standard Delphi/C++ function, representing integer floor of the real number.

The fit routine can start search for the f_0 from the expected frequency:

$$f_{exp} = f_{base}/8 - f_{ref}(820nm) - N_{Tsunami} \times f_{rep}^{Tsunami}/2$$